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“MEALS”

Thinking of my retirement was full of excitement and expectations. Counting on my blessings and incentives or cash to be received was overwhelming. But I was wrong, it was really the start of my responsibilities ahead. My mother died. My elder sister had to undergo dialysis 3 times a week. I thought it was a moment of my joy on my retirement, thinking of travelling abroad, buying things I like most.

I was wrong. Because I stand as a savior of my sick elder sister. Imagine the “gastos” of dialysis 3 times a week was no joke. Helping her spent for her dialysis almost got my budget. But I thank God, until now she is still with us during our meals!

